

**REVIEW: MARIN MANOLESCU (COORD.) – THE
PARENTS AND THE SCHOOL, EDITURA
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The title of the book "The Parents and the School" (published by the Editura Universitară in 2024), inspiringly expresses the main intention of the volume's coordinator – PhD Professor Emeritus Marin Manolescu – to emphasize the need for the social opening of the school, for the intensification of the connection between teachers and students' families. The fundamental role of the relationships between parents and the social environment is masterfully symbolized by the concept of "educational fortress", which refers to the importance of the educational community, of collective identity, especially in the context of the development of new information and communication technologies.

The collective volume, coordinated by PhD. Professor Emeritus Marin Manolescu, with a total of 284 pages, brings together 22 excellent studies by several specialists in the field of educational sciences in Romania (among which

we mention: PhD Professor Claudiu Marian Bunăiașu - University of Craiova, PhD Professor Florica Orțan - University of Oradea, Senior Lecturer PhD Aida Cornelia Stoian - University of Craiova), focused on the idea of the importance of the relationship between parents and school, in the context of postmodern pedagogy. Meticulously elaborated studies, such as that of PhD Professor Florica Orțan, from the University of Oradea, entitled "Organizational culture and the impact on parents and educational partners" insist on institutional aspects, demonstrating, among other things, that the central core of the postmodern school is organizational culture. In the same way, another study, elaborated by Professor Roxana Maria Gavrilă, entitled "Parents and the authority of the school institution" prefers to analyze issues related to status, especially the implications of theories regarding the main role of parents in the education of children, of course in partnership with school institutions. Yet another study, which substantiates the key ideas of the work, such as the one elaborated by Professor Elena Iavorschi, entitled "Parental involvement – added value in the educational space", supports the principle that parental involvement brings added value to the formative action of the school. We also appreciate the excellent study by PhD Professor Claudiu Marian Bunăiașu, entitled "Perspectives of approach and strategies for the development of parental competences" which brings to the fore the concept of "parental competence", from the perspective of educational sciences, which has been insufficiently analyzed in the specialized literature.

In conclusion, the work "Parents and School" responds to a deep need in the specialized literature, to strengthen communication and collaboration between the main actors involved in the educational process and to outline new paradigms for approaching the relationship between them.